

Prediction of the Stress-Strain Curve of Unidirectional Metal Matrix Composite

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ABSTRACT

We will focus on the prediction of the stress-strain curve of unidirectional (continuous and short fiber) metal matrix composites, especially its first and second stages. The analytical method used in this study is based on the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method modified for a large volume fraction of fiber. For the prediction of the second stage of the stress-strain curve, we have used the Mori-Tanaka's model modified for a large volume fraction of fiber. The present analytical results are compared with a limited number of experimental data. A good agreement between the theoretical and experimental results is obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Lightweight, high stiffness, and high strength metal matrix composites are desirable for structural components such as turbine blades and automobile engine components which operate at elevated temperatures. The research in the area of metal matrix composites was very active in the late 1960's, then its effort was slowed down in the last decade. However, due to the limited resources in metals and crude oils and the high demand for new materials with unique properties, the use of metal matrix composites has recently been of great interest as energy saving materials to various industries throughout the world.

Unlike polymer or ceramic-based composites, the metal matrix of metal matrix composites undergo plastic deformation more or less beyond a certain level of the applied stress. Kelly and Lilholt (1) defined various stages of the stress-strain curve of a composite as:

- the first stage : both matrix and fiber remain elastic
- the second stage: the matrix deforms plastically and the fiber remains elastic
- the third stage : both matrix and fiber deform plastically

The above three stages may not be always applicable to any metal matrix composite. The existence of the second and third stages depends on the type of matrix and fiber materials.

A study on the prediction of the first stage has been well made in the last two decades. For the case of unidirectional continuous metal matrix composites, even a simple rule of mixture can predict accurately its first stage. However, for the case of short-fiber or particulate reinforced composites, the prediction on its first stage must be based on the model which takes into account the interaction between fibers. One of the simplest models in this category is the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method modified for a large volume fraction of fibers (2-5).

The prediction of the second stage of metal matrix composites (W-Cu) has been made by Kelly and Lilholt who used the Hill's axisymmetrical model (6). They found that the discrepancy between the predicted and experimental slopes of the second stage becomes larger as the volume fraction of fiber increases. Tanaka and Mori (7) experienced the same trend as Kelly and Lilholt even though the Tanaka-Mori's model is different from that of Kelly and Lilholt. The Tanaka-Mori's model is based on the original Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method which is valid only for a small volume fraction of inhomogeneity. Indeed, their theoretical results agree well with the experimental ones as far as a small volume fraction is concerned. In this paper, we modified the Tanaka-Mori's model for larger volume fractions of fiber.

A limited number of experimental data of metal matrix composites are all on the case of unidirection continuous fiber and are compared with the theoretical results. We have also made a theoretical prediction on the first and second stages of a typical short-fiber metal matrix composite Al-SiC system.

FORMULATION

First Stage

An infinite elastic body which contains inhomogeneities and is subject to the applied stress σ_{ij}^0 is shown in Fig. 1. Let the domains of the infinite body and inhomogeneities be denoted by D and Ω , respectively. Hence the domain of the matrix becomes $D-\Omega$. The elastic constants of the matrix and inhomogeneities are denoted by C_{ijkl}^0 and C_{ijkl} , respectively.

Inhomogeneities can be considered as continuous fibers or ellipsoidal short fibers or particles. We assume that all inhomogeneities are aligned in the uniaxial loading direction and have the same size. Further, we assume that the matrix and inhomogeneities are linearly elastic and isotropic. Under the applied stress σ_{ij}^0 the average of the total stress in the matrix is given by $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_M$ (3-5) and

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_M = C_{ijkl}^0 \bar{e}_{kl} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{e}_{ij} is the average strain disturbance of the matrix due to all Ω and $\langle \rangle$ denotes the volume averaged quantity. A single fiber is introduced into the composite D , then the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method (2-5) yields in D .

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^0 + \sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}^0 (e_{kl}^0 + \bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - e_{kl}^*) \\ &= C_{ijkl} (e_{kl}^0 + \bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij} and e_{kl} are the disturbance of the stress and strain due to this single fiber, respectively. e_{kl}^* is the fictitious eigenstrain which has non-vanishing components in Ω and becomes zero outside Ω . For the entire domain D , the following relation always holds,

$$\sigma_{ij}^0 = C_{ijkl}^0 e_{kl}^0 \quad (3)$$

With eq. (3), eq. (2) yields

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^0 (\bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - e_{kl}^*) \quad (4)$$

Following Eshelby, we have

$$e_{kl} = S_{klmn} e_{mn}^* \quad (5)$$

where S_{klmn} is the Eshelby's tensor which depends on C_{ijkl}^0 and the geometry of Ω . Since the disturbed stress σ_{ij} must satisfy $\int_D \sigma_{ij} dV = 0$, we obtain

$$(1-f) \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_M + f \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_\Omega = 0 \quad (6)$$

where f is the volume fraction of Ω , and the subscripts M and Ω denote the matrix and fiber phase, respectively.

Eliminating e_{ij} through eq. (5), we have two unknowns, i.e. \bar{e}_{ij} and e_{ij}^* . From eqs. (2) and (6), we have

$$e_{11}^* = e_{22}^* = A_1 (\sigma_o / E_o) \quad (7)$$

$$e_{33}^* = B_1 (\sigma_o / E_o). \quad (8)$$

A_1 and B_1 are given in Appendix A. In the above derivation we have assumed that the composite system of Fig. 1 gives rise to a transverse isotropy and the resulting stress and strain field in each fiber also becomes transverse isotropic, i.e., $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22}$, $e_{11}^* = e_{22}^*$. We can compute the effective stiffness of the composite C_{ijkl}^C by using the equivalence of the strain energies (3,4):

$$\frac{1}{2} \sigma_o^o \cdot C_{ijkl}^{C-1} \sigma_{kl} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij}^o \cdot C_{ijkl}^o \sigma_{kl}^o + \frac{1}{2} f \sigma_{ij}^o \cdot e_{ij}^* \quad (9)$$

We consider here the uniaxially applied stress σ^o along the x_3 -axis as shown in Fig. 1. Then the effective longitudinal Young's modulus E_L of the composite can be obtained.

$$\frac{E_L}{E_o} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{E_o}{\sigma_o} f e_{33}^*} \quad (10)$$

where E_o is the Young's modulus of the matrix and e_{33}^* is the eigenstrain given by eq. (8). The details of the above formulations is given in (8).

Second Stage

Next, we will predict the stress-strain curve of the composite's second stage. Following Tanaka and Mori (7), we consider an infinite elastic body which contains inhomogeneities that have initially ($\sigma_{ij}^o = 0$) the equivalent eigenstrains of $e_{11}^p = \epsilon/2$, $e_{22}^p = \epsilon/2$ and $e_{33}^p = -\epsilon$, and is subjected to the applied stress σ_{ij}^o . This model is equivalent to the model in that plastic deformation which occurs only in the matrix, as shown in Fig. 2. We consider the interaction between fibers that was not introduced in the Tanaka-Mori's model. The definition of D , Ω , C_{ijkl}^o , and C_{ijkl} are the same as for the first stage.

Following Eshelby, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^o + \sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}^o (e_{kl}^o + \bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - e_{kl}^{**}) \\ &= C_{ijkl} (e_{kl}^o + \bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} + e_{kl}^p) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\sigma_{ij}^o = C_{ijkl}^o e_{kl}^o \quad \text{in } D \quad (12)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_M = C_{ijkl}^o \bar{e}_{kl} \quad \text{in } D-\Omega \quad (13)$$

and

$$e_{kl} = S_{klmn} e_{mn}^{**} \quad (14)$$

\bar{e}_{kl} is the average strain disturbance of the matrix due to all Ω . e_{kl}^{**} is the fictitious eigenstrain which has non-vanishing components in Ω and becomes zero outside Ω . From eqs. (11) and (12), the stress disturbance σ_{ij} is obtained as

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^o (\bar{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - e_{kl}^{**}). \quad (15)$$

Since $\int_D \sigma_{ij} dV = 0$, we have

$$(1-f) \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_M + f \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_\Omega = 0. \quad (16)$$

With eqs. (11), (12) and (13), eq. (16) is reduced to

$$\bar{e}_{ij} + f(e_{ij} - e_{ij}^{**}) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Eliminating e_{ij} through eq. (14), we have two unknowns, i.e. \bar{e}_{ij} and e_{ij}^{**} . From eqs. (11) and (16), we obtain

$$e_{11}^{**} = A_1(\sigma_o/E_o) + A_2 \epsilon \quad (18)$$

$$e_{33}^{**} = B_1(\sigma_o/E_o) + B_2 \epsilon. \quad (19)$$

A_1 , A_2 , B_1 , and B_2 are given in Appendix B. By use of eqs. (15), (18), and (19) we express the stress disturbance σ_{ij} in Ω in terms of e_{ij}^{**} .

$$\sigma_{11} = (1-f)E_o(H_{11}e_{11}^{**} + H_{12}e_{33}^{**}) \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_{33} = (1-f)E_o(H_{21}e_{11}^{**} + H_{22}e_{33}^{**}) \quad (21)$$

where H_{11} , H_{12} , H_{21} and H_{22} are given in Appendix B.

In order to obtain the second stage of the stress-strain curve, we apply the energy balance equation (5):

$$\delta U + \delta Q = 0 \quad (22)$$

where U is the total potential energy of Fig. 2, δQ is the total plastic work and δ is the change due to the change in the plastic strain ϵ_{ij}^p in the matrix. U in this problem is given by

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_D (\sigma_{ij}^o + \sigma_{ij}) (u_{i,j}^o + \bar{u}_{i,j} + u_{i,j} - \epsilon_{ij}^p) dV - \int_{|D|} \sigma_{ij}^o n_j (u_i^o + \bar{u}_i + u_i) dS \quad (23)$$

where $|D|$ is the surface of D and u_i^o , \bar{u}_i and u_i are the displacement components corresponding to strains e_{ij}^o , \bar{e}_{ij} and e_{ij} , respectively. After having taken δ on U and using $\sigma_{ij}^o n_j = 0$ on $|D|$, $\int_D \sigma_{ij}^o dV = 0$, we can reduce δU to

$$\delta U = -\delta \epsilon_{ij}^p \{ (1-f) \sigma_{ij}^o - f \sigma_{ij} \}. \quad (24)$$

On the other hand, δQ is given by

$$\delta Q = (1-f) \sigma_y \delta \epsilon_{33}^p. \quad (25)$$

It is noted that δU and δQ are expressed per unit volume. From eqs. (24) and (25), we obtain

$$\sigma_o = \frac{\sigma_y}{P_1} + f \left(\frac{P_2}{P_1} \right) E_o \cdot \epsilon \quad (26)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are given in Appendix B. We note in passing that when $\bar{e}_{ij} = 0$, then our results become identical to those of Tanaka and Mori (7).

For metal matrix composites which have brittle fibers, the fibers will not undergo plastic deformation. Thus, the end of the second stage can be identified as the failure of the composite. We intend to give a simple criterion here to predict the composite failure strain ϵ_f for such a metal matrix composite. Our criterion is to set the fiber stress equal to the fiber breaking stress σ_{fB} . This will be a conservative estimate for ϵ_f . To this end, the fiber axial stress, σ_f is obtained from eqs. (18), (19), (21) and (26) as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{fB} &= \sigma_o + \sigma_{33} \\ &= \sigma_o (1-f) E_o (H_{21} e_{11}^{**} + H_{22} e_{33}^{**}) \\ &= R_1 \sigma_y + R_2 E_o \cdot \epsilon_f \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where σ_y is the yield stress of the matrix, and

$$R_1 = \frac{1}{P_1} \{ 1 + (1-f) (H_{21} A_1 + H_{22} B_1) \}$$

$$R_2 = f P_2 R_1 + (1-f) (H_{21} A_2 + H_{22} B_2).$$

The composite failure strain ϵ_f is obtained from eq. (27)

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{\sigma_{fB} - R_1 \sigma_y}{R_2 E_o}. \quad (28)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First, we compare our calculation with the experimental results of Kelly and Lilholt (1). Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curves of the copper reinforced with aligned continuous tungsten fibers. Solid curves are the experimental results of Kelly and Lilholt, dash-dot curves are the theoretical results of Tanaka and Mori (7), and broken curves are present results. Mechanical properties of copper and tungsten used in our calculation are listed in Table 1. Since Tanaka and Mori did not consider the interaction between fibers, their calculation was effective only for a small volume fraction, i.e., $f = 0.043$. While our theoretical prediction indicates a fairly good fitting to the experimental results in the wide range of fiber volume fraction.

Figure 4 shows the stress-strain curve of FP(Al_2O_3) - magnesium system. The solid line is the experimental result of Dhingra and Krueger (9), and the broken one is based on the present model. We also have plotted in this figure the breaking stress σ_B of the composite as an open circle. In computing σ_B , the fiber breaking stress $\sigma_{fB} = 143 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ was used together with eq. (28). It follows that a good agreement between the experimental theoretical results is

obtained for the first and second stages of the stress-strain curve.

Figure 5 demonstrates the stress-strain curve of short-fiber metal matrix composites where the SiC-Al system was used and its mechanical properties are also listed in Table 1. The aspect ratios of the short-fiber $l/d = 2, 5, 10$ and 50 are used in Fig. 5. It follows from Fig. 5 that the stiffness and work-hardening rate of the composite increase with l/d .

Table 1

Material	Young's Modulus (Kg/mm ²)	Poisson's Ratio
Copper	12,000	0.33
Tungsten (20 $\mu\phi$)	38,100	0.28
Magnesium	4,550	0.35
FP (Al ₂ O ₃)	38,500	0.20
Al-Alloy	7,200	0.30
SiC	39,600	0.30

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REFERENCES

1. Kelly, A., and Lilholt, H. "Stress-Strain Curve of a Fibre-Reinforced Composite." *Phil. Mag.*, Vol. 20, 1969, pp. 311-328.
2. Mori, T., and Tanaka, K. "Average Stress in Matrix and Average Elastic Energy of Materials with Misfitting Inclusions." *Acta Metall.*, Vol. 21, 1973, pp. 571-574.
3. Taya, M., and Mura, T. "On Stiffness and Strength of an Aligned Short-Fiber Reinforced Composite Containing Fiber-End Cracks Under Uniaxial Applied Stress." *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 48, 1981, pp. 361-367.
4. Taya, M., and Chou, T. W. "On Two Kinds of Ellipsoidal Inhomogeneities in an Infinite Elastic Body: Application to a Hybrid Composite." *Intl. J. Solids and Struct.*, Vol. 17, 1981, pp. 553-563.
5. Mura, T. *Micromechanics of Defects in Solids*. Noordhoff International Publishing, 1981 (in press).
6. Hill, R. "Theory of Mechanical Properties of Fiber-Strengthened Materials: II. Inelastic Behavior." *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 12, 1964, pp. 213-218.
7. Tanaka, K., and Mori, T. "The Hardening of Crystals by Non-Deforming Particles and Fibers." *Acta Metall.*, Vol. 18, 1970, pp. 931-941.
8. Takao, Y., Chou, T. W., and Taya, M. "Effective Longitudinal Young's Modulus of Misoriented Short Fiber Composites." *J. Appl. Mech.*, (in press).
9. Dhingra, A., and Krueger, W. H. "New Engineering Material - Magnesium Castings Reinforced with DuPont Continuous Alumina FP," Presented at the 36th World Conf. on Magnesium, Oslo, Norway, June 25-26, 1979.

APPENDIX A

A_1 and B_1 in eqs. (7) and (8) are given by

$$A_1 = \frac{(D_{11}C_{12} - D_{12}C_{11})}{(C_{21}C_{12} - C_{11}C_{22})} \quad (A1)$$

$$B_1 = \frac{(D_1 C_{21} - D_2 C_{11})}{(C_{21} C_{12} - C_{11} C_{22})} \quad (A2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + \bar{\mu})}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)(S_{1111} + S_{1122}) + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{3311} + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + \bar{\mu})}{\bar{\mu}_0} f + \frac{\lambda}{\mu_0} + 1 \\ C_{12} &= \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{2\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{3333} + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + \bar{\mu})}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{1133} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{2\bar{\mu}_0} f + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu_0} \\ C_{21} &= \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)(S_{1111} + S_{1122}) + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu})}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{3311} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\bar{\mu}_0} f + \frac{\lambda}{\mu_0} \\ C_{22} &= \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu})}{2\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{3333} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\bar{\mu}_0} (1-f)S_{1133} + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu})}{2\bar{\mu}_0} f + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu_0} + 1 \\ D_1 &= -\frac{\bar{\lambda}}{2\bar{\mu}_0} (1 - 2\nu_0) + \frac{\bar{\mu}}{\bar{\mu}_0} \nu_0 \\ D_2 &= -\frac{\bar{\lambda}}{2\bar{\mu}_0} (1 - 2\nu_0) - \frac{\bar{\mu}}{\bar{\mu}_0} \end{aligned} \quad (A3)$$

where $\bar{\lambda} = \lambda - \lambda_0$, $\bar{\mu} = \mu - \mu_0$. In the above equations, λ , μ are Lamé's constants of the fiber, λ_0 , μ_0 and ν_0 are Lamé's constants and Poisson's ratio of the matrix and S_{ijkl} are the Eshelby's tensors (see the details of S_{ijkl} in (3,4)).

APPENDIX B

A_1 and B_1 in eqs. (18) and (19) are identical to those given in Appendix A, eqs. (A1) and (A2). A_2 and B_2 are given by

$$A_2 = \frac{(C_{22} D_3 - C_{12} D_4)}{(C_{11} C_{22} - C_{21} C_{12})} \quad (B1)$$

$$B_2 = \frac{(C_{11} D_4 - C_{21} D_3)}{(C_{11} C_{22} - C_{21} C_{12})} \quad (B2)$$

where C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{21} and C_{22} are given by (A3) and

$$D_3 = \frac{1}{2} (\mu/\mu_0), \quad D_4 = -(\mu/\mu_0). \quad (B3)$$

H_{11} , H_{12} , H_{21} and H_{22} in eqs. (20) and (21) are given as

$$\begin{aligned} H_{11} &= \frac{1}{(1+\nu_0)} \left[\frac{2\nu_0}{(1-2\nu_0)} (S_{1111} + S_{1122} + S_{3311} - 1) + S_{1111} + S_{1122} - 1 \right] \\ H_{12} &= \frac{1}{(1+\nu_0)} \left[\frac{\nu_0}{(1-2\nu_0)} (S_{3333} + 2S_{1133} - 1) + S_{1133} \right] \\ H_{21} &= \frac{1}{(1+\nu_0)} \left[\frac{2\nu_0}{(1-2\nu_0)} (S_{1111} + S_{1122} + S_{3311} - 1) + 2S_{3311} \right] \\ H_{22} &= \frac{1}{(1+\nu_0)} \left[\frac{\nu_0}{(1-2\nu_0)} (S_{3333} + 2S_{1133} - 1) + S_{3333} - 1 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (B4)$$

P_1 and P_2 defined in eq. (26) are given by

$$P_1 = 1 - f \{ A_1 (H_{21} - H_{11}) + B_1 (H_{22} - H_{12}) \}, \quad P_2 = A_2 (H_{21} - H_{11}) + B_2 (H_{22} - H_{12}) \quad (B5)$$

Fig. 1. The model for the first stage.

Fig. 2. The model for the second stage.

Fig. 4. The stress-strain curve of FP fiber-magnesium composite.

Fig. 3. The stress-strain curve of Cu-W composites.

Fig. 5. Predicted stress-strain curves of SiC-Al composites.